

A New Spot Test for the Detection of Cobalt

S. B. SAXENA*, R. N. AGARWAL & A. GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, Madhav Institute of
Technology & Science, Gwalior (M.P.)

Manuscript received 6 August, 1976, accepted
10 February 1977.

THE authors earlier reported that 2-hydroxy-3-nitro-5-methyl-acetophenone oxime (HNMA) forms a bright-red chelate with cobalt at pH 4.5 and above¹.

The colour of the metal complex is so characteristic and sharp that it can form the basis for a reliable spot-test for the detection of cobalt.

Under the condition of the test (pH 5), Pd²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺, Fe³⁺ are other metals which give solid chelates of different colours. Al³⁺, Cr³⁺, Ca²⁺, Ba²⁺, Sr²⁺, Li⁺, Mg²⁺, Mn²⁺, Ce⁴⁺, Zr⁴⁺, Th⁴⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺, Hg²⁺, Bi³⁺ neither give a solid complex nor appear to make any characteristic colour change to interfere with the test.

Experimental

Place a few grains (25 mgms) of crystalline sodium acetate, a drop of the solution to be tested and a drop of 1.0% ethanolic solution of the reagent on a spot plate in the order. The formation of a deep red precipitate indicates the presence of Cobalt.

Identification limit : 1 μ
Dilution limit : 1 : 50,000
1 : 25,000 (in presence of interfering ions).

As expected, copper, palladium, nickel, iron and zinc interfere with the test. Interference due to copper and palladium can be overcome by precipitating out these metals at pH 1-2 and performing the test with supernatant liquid as above. Iron (Fe³⁺) can be masked by adding a drop of 10% sodium or potassium fluoride solution before the addition of the reagent.

It is not possible to test cobalt in the presence of a large excess of zinc and nickel which give canary yellow and green precipitates respectively under test conditions. However, cobalt can be tested reliably in the presence of upto 5 fold excess of these metals. The colour of the precipitate in such cases will vary from red to brown depending upon the concentration of the interfering metals viz., nickel and zinc.

Amongst the anions NO₃⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, SO₄²⁻, ClO₄⁻ were tried and were found not to interfere with the test even when present in severalfold excess. Desai and Gandhi² used *o*-hydroxy propiophenone and butyrophenone oximes for spot test detection of Iron.

* For correspondence

References

1. R. Nath, S. C. Nautiyal, and H. Singh, *Labdev, J. Sci., Tech.* (India), 1974, 12A (2), 53-8.
2. M. N. Desai and M. H. Gandhi. *Chem., & Industry* 1968, 20, 653.

A Variable Frequency, Variable Displacement, Glass Encased Gas Recirculation Pump

JOHN CECE, KASTURI GADGIL, KRISHNA MAIR
and
RICHARD D. GONZALEZ*

Department of Chemistry, University of Rhode Island,
Kingston, Rhode Island 02881 U.S.A.

Manuscript received 3 March 1976, revised 27 January
1977, accepted 24 February 1977.

RECIRCULATION pumps, provide a more satisfactory way of studying kinetics and mechanisms of reactions taking place in static reactors as a more homogeneous gas phase is assured. In particular, for studies occurring at the surface of a solid catalyst, mass transfer effects and concentration gradients can lead to erroneous interpretation of the data. If the gas phase is continually circulated over the solid catalyst, these effects can be diminished although not entirely eliminated. In the design of a recirculation pump, it is essential that the pump surface be contamination free. Several designs have been reported in the literature¹⁻⁴ but none are entirely satisfactory. Some of these designs incorporate metal parts and lubricants exposed to the gas phase whereas others, rely on gravity for the downstroke resulting in an unequal pressure differential for the upward and downward motion of the piston. There is one design which is nearly satisfactory⁴, however the electronic design is cumbersome in that energization of the solenoids is accomplished by a microswitch which is not only expensive but needs frequent replacement.

To circumvent this problem, we have incorporated several of the better features of the pump described by Chambers et al.⁴, and redesigned the electronics in such a way that microswitches and cams are not necessary. The result is the Variable Frequency, Variable Displacement pump described in this communication. We have found this pump to be inexpensive in its construction as well as trouble-free in its operation.

*To whom queries concerning this paper should be made.

The pump, shown in Figure 1, is encased in a glass tube made from pyrex and has an outer water circulating jacket which is necessary to dissipate the heat generated by the coils. The two solenoids are

rectifier (SCR) of small current capacity triggered by a collector coupled to a stable multivibrator made from n-p-n transistors (Figure 2). The n-p-n transistors can only be in either the saturated or cut-off

Figure 1. Schematic drawing of pump.

symmetrically wound over the glass jacket with an equal number of turns of insulated copper wire as shown in Figure 1 which also shows the dimensions of the pump. They were held in place and separated from one another by slabs of plexiglass which were fitted over the water jacket. Approximately 750 turns of copper wire 0.69 mm in diameter for each solenoid were alternately energized by a half wave rectified 60 cycle AC, the voltage of which could be controlled through a variac. The current through each solenoid was controlled by silicon-controlled

position. The circuit is such that when one is saturated, the other is cut off. The frequency of alternation is determined by resistors R_1 and R_2 and capacitors C_1 and C_2 . When $R_1 = R_2 = R$ and $C_1 = C_2 = C$, the frequency is given by $1/1.38RC$. The resistors R_1 and R_2 are simultaneously varied from 50 K Ω to lower values as the output frequency is increased from 1.5 cycles.

The voltage at the collector end of each of the transistors Q_1 and Q_2 is applied to the base of Q_3

Figure 2. Diagram of pump circuit, T, 110V-12V 700 mA transformer ; D_4, D_5, D_6, D_7 , 50V 250 mA diodes or one 50 mV 500 mA bridge rectifier ; C_3 , 200 μ F 50V electrolytic capacitor ; S_1, S_2 , 200V PIV 6A Silicon controlled rectifiers ; R_7, R_8, R_9 , 100 Ω 1/2W resistors ; R_1, R_2 100 K Ω double-pole potentiometer ; R_3, R_4 , 1K Ω 1/4W resistors ; R_5, R_6 , 2K Ω /12W resistors ; C_1, C_2 , 10 μ F electrolytic capacitors ; Q_3, Q_4, Q_5, Q_6 MPS 6573 transistors ; D_1, D_2 , 1N 914 diodes ; D_3 , 1N 3020 diode.

and Q_4 which act as emitter followers. The square-wave-forms at the emitters of Q_3 and Q_4 are applied to the gates of S_1 and S_2 through current-limiting resistors R_7 and R_8 . The diodes, D_1 and D_2 , increase the turn-on voltage of each transistor by 0.7 volts, thereby preventing both transistors from getting turned on at the same time. The diode D_3 protects this circuit. When the square-wave is applied to the gate of the SCR, the gate current varies between zero and a fixed value (high enough to latch the device). When the gate current is zero, it is open, and when the gate current is large, it acts as a p-n diode. Since each solenoid is connected to an AC supply, with an SCR in series, the current flows in one direction in one-half cycle only. Due to the nature of the astable multivibrator, the wave-forms are complimentary and hence while one solenoid is on, the other remains cut off.

During normal operation, the pumping frequency is of the order of 40 to 50 oscillations per minute with an average displacement of about 5 cm.

We advise the following precautions in the construction of this pump: (1) each solenoid should have an equal number of turns, (2) since the current is inversely proportional to the number of turns, heating can be minimized by using as few turns as possible, (3) the piston should be made of soft iron rod, (4) the length of the piston should be 1-1/2 times the length of each solenoid and (5) teflon o-rings should be used to fit the piston to the glass tube as they provide minimum friction.

Acknowledgement

We are grateful to Mr. Andrew Kocsi for assistance in the design of the glass portions of the pump.

References

1. W. R. Bennett, *Rev. Sci. Instr.*, 1957, 28, 1092.
2. C. J. Sterner, *Rev. Sci. Instr.*, 1960, 31, 1159.
3. N. Yu Artyukh and A. F. Nikolenko, *Kinetika i Kataliz*, 1960, 1, 620.
4. R. P. Chambers, N. A. Dougharty and M. Boudart, *J. Catal.*, 1965, 4, 625.

Chemical Constituents of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* Stem-Bark and Flowers

K. K. AWASTHI and (Mrs.) K. MISRA

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad,
Allahabad-211002, (India)

Manuscript received 15 November 1976, accepted
3 March 1977

IN an earlier publication¹, we have reported the isolation of gallic acid, ellagic acid, leucodelphi-

nidin and an ellagitannin from the stem bark of *C. pulcherrima*. Some other constituents present in the bark and flowers of this plant have now been investigated.

The hot ethanolic extract of the powdered bark was fractionated into (i) petroleum ether soluble; (ii) ether soluble and (iii) ethyl acetate soluble fraction. Fraction (i) yielded a steroid (A), fraction (ii) an acid (B) and fraction (iii) gave two compounds (C) and (D).

Compound (A) (β -sitosterol) :

It was isolated as white crystalline compound, m.p. 138°, (found: C, 83.92; H, 12.32%; Calc.: for $C_{28}H_{48}O$, C, 84.06; H, 12.08%). It gave all colour tests of steroids. It was identified as β -sitosterol by m.m.p. and co-chromatography with an authentic sample and also by its acetate and digitonide.

Compound (B) (Sebacic acid) :

This compound was isolated as white crystals, m.p. 130-32° (found, C, 59.32; H, 9.02%; Calc., for $C_{18}H_{34}O_2$: C, 59.40; H, 8.91%). Chemical tests indicated it to be a saturated aliphatic acid. Its IR spectrum was characteristic of a polymethylenic acid. It was identified as sebacic acid by m.m.p. and co-chromatography with an authentic sample and also by its amide formation.

Compound (C) (Quercetin-7-O- β -D(+)-glucopyranoside) (Quercimeritrin) :

The compound was isolated as pale yellow crystalline compound, m.p., 248-50° (d), (found, C, 54.37; H, 4.42%; Calc. for $C_{21}H_{20}O_{12}$: C, 54.31; H, 4.31%). It gave positive Molisch test and did not reduce Fehling solution, thereby indicating its glycosidic nature. Acid hydrolysis of the glycoside yielded an aglycone, $C_{15}H_{10}O_7$, m.p. 313-15° and a reducing sugar which was identified as D(+) glucose by mixed paper chromatography and osazone formation. Quantitative estimation of sugar showed it to be a monoglucoside.

The aglycone was found to be flavonoid in nature by its characteristic colour reactions. From its spectral studies (UV and IR) and preparation of derivatives i.e., acetate and methyl ether the aglycone was shown to be quercetin. Position of the glucose moiety was ascertained by taking shifts with different reagents in the ultraviolet region. A bathochromic shift of the long wavelength, band I with sodium acetate and boric acid² in ethanol with aglycone (18 nm) as well as glycoside (16 nm) suggested the presence of a free catechol unit in both. Aglycone and glycoside both gave bathochromic shift of long wavelength band I 58 nm and 54 nm respectively with ethanolic aluminium chloride³ showing thereby the presence of free 5-hydroxyl